

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGINEERING COMPUTER GRAPHICS THROUGH THE PTS (PROFESSIONAL TECHNOLOGY SYSTEM) PLATFORM

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Abstract. *While teaching has been a priority in the traditional education system, the use of digital technologies is gaining significant importance in the era of informatization. The priority is shifting towards teaching students how to learn. Therefore, it is necessary to replace the “teacher-textbook-student” paradigm of education with the “student-textbook-teacher” paradigm. The shortcomings of the work carried out on teaching engineering computer graphics programs in higher education institutions based on the method of mutual comparison have been eliminated.*

Keywords: *digital technology, educational technologies, multimedia, digitization.*

Introduction

In the Action Strategy on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, “further improvement of the continuous education system, increasing the opportunities for quality education services, continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern requirements of the labor market” (1) is defined as an important task. In implementing this task, the development of design skills of higher education students depends on their spatial imagination, creative activity, and proficiency in designing practical issues related to the field. These qualities are enhanced through the widespread use of digital technologies in education.

In higher education institutions, in the bachelor's programs of vocational education, the subjects of "Methodology" are taught in the upper courses to improve the professional training of future teachers. These subjects not only cover traditional approaches to teaching but also develop skills in applying the most advanced methods. However, this subject does not have sufficient capacity to adequately address the issues of creating methodological and didactic materials.

Thus, achieving a high level of professional-pedagogical training for a technology education teacher requires the presence of the following conditions: the degree of professional and personal formation of the future technology education teacher is closely linked to the overall effectiveness of the pedagogical system that illuminates the essence of the organized process; the organizational management of the processes ensuring the professional formation of the future technology education teacher should be improved in a purposeful manner; reflective management guarantees the achievement of the intended goal in the professional formation of the future technology education teacher.

(2) In the professional development of future technology education teachers, professional graphic competence and development are closely interconnected: on the one hand, professional

graphic competence is formed during the professional development process; on the other hand, it serves as a key indicator of the individual's manifestation as a specialist.

Despite the growing interest in the issue of professional graphic competence, questions regarding the nature, structure, dynamics, and functions of this phenomenon remain unresolved and fraught with numerous ambiguities. In our view, the primary reason for this lies in the insufficient study of the social qualities applied to the place of professional graphic competence within the overall structure of the individual. To investigate the problem of professional graphic competence, it is first necessary to understand the position this reality occupies within the system of personal qualities and the role it plays in the individual's professional and social self-awareness.

In this regard, the problem arises of training vocational education teachers who can use ready-made software-based educational-methodological developments or create their own. To form the knowledge, skills, and competencies of future teachers in pedagogical design within the electronic information educational environment during the vocational education process, it is expedient to introduce the (PTS) platform. This platform ensures that future vocational education teachers meet the requirements of the state educational standard for the relevant course in the curricula developed for vocational education institutions, in terms of modern pedagogical technologies, their application in the educational-upbringing process, and the consistent equipping of the lesson process with Professional Technology.

The extensive use of digital technologies by students serves to accelerate scientific and technical development in society and, on this basis, to achieve socio-economic progress. "Introducing modern forms and methods of teaching, information and multimedia technologies into the educational process, providing higher education institutions with modern educational technology and laboratory equipment, educational and methodological literature, supporting and encouraging scientific research and innovation activities, and taking measures to organize and develop modern scientific laboratories in higher education institutions" (3) ensure the training of competitive personnel and the demonstration of their professional mobility and creativity.

The digitization of all spheres of human activity has led to the transformation of century-old pedagogical technologies. New teaching tools require reconsidering the fundamental issues of pedagogy: who should be taught in the higher education system at the current stage of societal development, what the content of education should be, and what forms and methods should be used as the basis for training higher education specialists (4). Taking the above into account, we consider the revision of the content of the engineering computer graphics subject to be one of the urgent problems in teaching this discipline. It is appropriate to consider the achievements of today's science and technology fields when reorganizing the content of digital technologies.

Didactic Principles and Their Digital Context

The analysis of studies devoted to the problems of teaching principles allows for the identification of didactic principles common to all subjects. Researchers agree on the nomenclature of didactic principles. However, the content of these principles is interpreted differently. Such principles include:

- the principle of education and upbringing;
- the principle of interconnection between theory and practice;
- the principle of scientificity;
- the principle of comprehensibility;
- the principle of compatibility and consistency;
- the principle of consciousness and creative activity;

- the principle of visibility;
- the principle of consistency in educational outcomes and the development of cognitive abilities;
- the principle of considering individual characteristics of learners and the collectivity of education;
- the principle of positive emotionality in education.

When dividing the content and process of education into two parts, traditional didactic principles can be conditionally divided into these two groups. The conditionality of separating didactic principles in this way is explained by their interdependence and interconnectedness. As an example, we cite the conditionality of separating the processes of education, upbringing, and development. The principles of educational content include:

- the principle of scientificity;
- the principle of comprehensibility;
- the principle of consistency;
- the principle of continuity;
- the principle of integrity;
- the principle of interconnection between theory and practice;
- the principle of continuity.

Principles of Content Selection:

The Principle of Scientificity. M.D. Dammer (5) demonstrated the development of the content of the scientificity principle. According to the research results, the content of this principle was first presented in 1950 by M.N. Skatkin in the form of eight requirements:

1. the scientific reliability of information delivered to students;
2. revealing the essence of ongoing events;
3. showing events in correlation;
4. displaying events in development and highlighting the sharp characteristics of this development;
5. introducing learners to the most important theories that enable correct dialectical-materialistic interpretation of events;
6. creating correct ideas in learners about knowing the world and the power of the human mind;
7. forming correct thoughts in students about absolute and relative truth;
8. introducing students to scientific research methods.

We agree with the opinion of Z.K. Meretukova and A.R. Chinazirova: “The principle of scientificity in education should take into account the existence of ‘scientific pluralism’ in the educational component. Different approaches to a single scientific problem expand students’ thinking scope and encourage them to search for truth” (6). The views of G.M. Chernabelskaya can be understood from the last words of her quote: “Scientific content is achieved not by giving students ready-made knowledge, but by introducing them to scientific research methods” (7, p. 18).

Taking all of the above into account, it can be stated that in the process of scientific and technical development, the volume of scientific knowledge that students must acquire is increasing, while the time allocated for studying the material remains unchanged. In our republic, the content of educational technologies and the method of teaching them have not changed in the last 25 years. Since 2022, only Autodesk’s AutoCAD software has been used in engineering

graphics and related fields in the Republic of Uzbekistan. However, students at foreign higher education institutions can master several digital programs. These programs pertain to constructive, functional, and technological systems. Considering that pedagogical higher education institutions train pedagogical personnel, we believe it is appropriate to use only programs related to the construction system.

In our opinion, the best way to make effective use of the time allocated to digital technologies and simultaneously ensure competitiveness is to teach several programs related to the design system by comparing them with each other. This is explained by the uniformity of the operating principles of the programs, their tasks, and the results achieved with their help. This, in turn, requires improving the requirements for students' knowledge, skills, and qualifications in the field of engineering computer graphics. An engineering computer graphics student should know the following:

- the history of digital technologies;
- the sections of digital technologies;
- the systems (PTS) included in the construction graphics section;
- digital technologies operating in the PTS system and their operating principles;
- electronic image formats;
- equipment panels used for drawing;
- algorithms for drawing an object based on its spatial position.

Conclusion

The best way to make effective use of the time allocated to engineering computer graphics and simultaneously ensure competitiveness is to teach several programs related to digital technologies by comparing them with each other. This is explained by the uniformity of the operating principles of the programs, their tasks, and the results achieved with their help. This, in turn, requires improving the requirements for students' knowledge, skills, and qualifications in the field of engineering computer graphics.

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